

Model of Psychological Readiness of a Coach to Make Decisions in Extreme Situations of Professional Activity

Oksana KHURTENKO¹,
Svitlana LIEBIDIEVA²,
Lina PERELYGINA³,
Oleksandr MORHUNOV⁴,
Vasyl OVCHARUK⁵,
Eduard MYKHLIUK⁶

¹Vinnitsia Mykhailo Kotsiubynskyi State Pedagogical University, Ukraine, kseniayrtenko@gmail.com

²National university of civil defence of Ukraine, Ukraine, lebedeva@nuczu.edu.ua

³National university of civil defence of Ukraine, Ukraine, perelugina@nuczu.edu.ua

⁴Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs, Ukraine, tspsfp1976@gmail.com

⁵Vinnitsia National Technical University, Ukraine, vvovcharuk@gmail.com

⁶National university of civil defence of Ukraine, Ukraine, muhlyk@nuczu.edu.ua

Abstract: *Inflated self-esteem provokes goal setting higher than the real possibilities, neglect of the necessary information, reduction of the probability of failure, minimization of efforts to achieve the goal, "relaxing" effect of success and a strong emotional experience of failure; the need to maintain the level of self-esteem leads to a protective ignoring of failures, the explanation of their external causes, which weakens the incentive to overcome them. Sharply inflated self-esteem can create at a certain stage of activity a zone of constant failures, reduced professional motivation. The consequence of low self-esteem is passivity, fear of responsibility, tendency to set too easy tasks, underestimation of the subjective probability of success, which disrupts the impact of failures. Obviously, the inadequacy of self-esteem becomes an obstacle to professional adaptation. As evidenced by our observations, it is characteristic that coaches who do not have a sufficient level of competence in the management of subordinates, have an inflated self-esteem. But also adequate high self-esteem, which is spontaneously formed in the process of professional training, can become a disorganizing factor, if it is not critically transferred from educational to professional activities. In this case, entering a professional activity, which is already characterized by a decrease in the stability of self-esteem, is complicated by its strong fluctuations. In addition, we found that there is no significant correlation between learning success and success in starting a professional activity. High self-esteem of a young specialist is often an obstacle to his acceptance into the team. The creative adaptive component, which prevails over the conformal one, is an interference at this stage.*

Keywords: *coach readiness model, inflated self-esteem, motivation of the coach activity, professional training, young specialists, management of subordinates.*

How to cite: Khurtenko, O., Liebidieva, S., Perelygina, L., Morhunov, O., Ovcharuk, V., & Mykhliuk, E. (2022). Model of Psychological Readiness of a Coach to Make Decisions in Extreme Situations of Professional Activity. *BRAIN. Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 13(1Sup1), 247-266.

<https://doi.org/10.18662/brain/13.1Sup1/317>

Introduction

Analysis of theoretical and methodological approaches to the study of the problem of psychological readiness of the individual to work, readiness to manage people allows us to state that there are two main approaches to determining its content and structure: functional and personal. Within the functional approach, psychological readiness is considered as a certain state of mental functions of the individual, which provides a high level of achievement in performing a particular activity, Karamushka (2000).

It should be noted that from the point of view of personal approach, psychological readiness is considered as a result of training, as an individual's readiness for a certain activity. In this regard, psychological readiness can be represented as a stable, integrated formation of personality, which includes a number of components that are adequate to the requirements of content and conditions of activity, which together allow the subject to more or less successfully implement it. Thus, at the personal level, readiness is considered as a manifestation of individual and personal qualities, due to the nature of future activities of a number of scientists Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, (1981); Ananiev, (1980); Bezliudnyi (2019); Gerasymova (2019); Maksymchuk (2020); Melnyk (2019); Nerubasska (2020); Onishchuk (2020); Sheremet (2019).

Psychological readiness for any activity at the functional level is represented as temporary readiness and efficiency, pre-start activation of mental functions, the ability to mobilize the necessary physical and mental resources for the implementation of activities (Chamata, 1960; Levitov, 1963).

Among the researchers who consider on a personal level readiness for professional activity sports psychologist Puni (1969). In his opinion, the problem of readiness is psychological and pedagogical (psychological in subject and pedagogical in means of forming readiness). In the structure of readiness, the author identifies the symptom complex of signs: volitional qualities, the necessary direction of intellectual processes, special observation, creative imagination, the optimal level of wall emotions, flexible attention, the ability to self-regulation. The author's approach to this problem makes it possible to explore readiness as a manifestation of individual and personal qualities, due to the nature of future activities (Puni, 1969).

In the context of management Orban-Lembrick (2001), presents the readiness of the individual as a psychological mechanism that allows us to

see the motivating effect of meaningful choice. At the same time, she notes that "the readiness of the leader's personality is a socially determined and mentally conditioned process, which finds its expression in a positive emotional and volitional attitude to management, it is a concentrated indicator of professionalism, it is a person's ability to reach the top (acme) skills, these are, finally, the real actions of the individual that contribute to the optimal and successful functioning and development of the organization" Orban-Lembrik (2001).

We are impressed by the opinion of the researcher Yu. Samarin, (1969), who argues that readiness as a psychological state of personality is an internal attitude to a certain behavior in solving problems facing a person, setting for active and appropriate action. The purpose of readiness is to facilitate the process of adaptation, to achieve success, for which it is necessary to master the operational, moral, mental, organizational aspects of the chosen profession.

Ukrainian psychologist Chamata (1960) understands the readiness to work as the formation of moral and psychological qualities of the individual, which determine the attitude to professional activity and ensure its successful implementation. The author considers the educational process to be the main means of forming readiness. However, according to the author, although objectively readiness is formed in the educational process, in practice this may not happen, which makes it necessary to introduce special measures that purposefully affect its formation and development.

Psychological readiness for activity in extreme conditions is considered by researcher Timchenko (1995). According to the author, to achieve readiness are necessary: adequate reflection of the specialty, professional skills, the ability to mobilize the necessary physical and mental resources for the implementation of activities.

At the functional level, psychological readiness is considered by Levitov (1963) and understands it as temporary readiness and ability to work. He sees its essence in the pre-start activation of mental functions. Its content is orientation in working conditions and creation of mental readiness for it. The problem of readiness is related to the broadest personal context. The author identifies three factors of individual readiness for professional activity: two psychological (a person's attitude to a particular job, its focus on this field and suitability for the profession) and pedagogical (mastering the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for this profession) (Levitov, 1963).

Shadrikov (1994) emphasizes that readiness can be seen not only as a working mobilization of professional and psychological opportunities, but

also as higher professionalism, based on various reserves selected by social experience and profession, compensation and substitutions generated by self-improvement of natural data, personal experience and practice, pedagogical school and own professional orientation.

A. Derkach (1981) considered the psychological readiness to perform professional functions from the standpoint of personal-activity approach. It is defined as a holistic manifestation of all aspects of personality (cognitive, emotional, motivational components). According to other scientists Barabanshchikov (1967), the formation of readiness means the creation of a system of such motives, attitudes, personality traits, accumulation of knowledge, skills, abilities, which, intensifying, provide a professional opportunity to effectively perform their functions. Since the improvement of activity and the formation of readiness for it is a two-way interrelated process, and the level of readiness for activity determines the optimal human performance and high productivity, the increase in readiness can be considered as a basis for improving efficiency.

Researcher of the psychological structure of personality Platonov (1986) identifies one of the values of readiness for work as one that is directly manifested in certain conditions and is the result of psychological training and psychological mobilization.

The model of psychological readiness of the coach to make decisions in extreme situations

Psychological readiness in a particular activity is understood as an intensive restructuring of this level of professionalism in the direction of its improvement, it is a characteristic of the psychological capabilities of the developing person, a characteristic of a certain stage of his mental development, its diversity, breadth, scale and range. Regardless of the type of activity, readiness is formed at all stages of professional development in the Higher Education Institute (HEI). As it develops, it becomes a condition and a means of organizing a reserve of personal activity, its property, created by professional activity or preparation for it (Skorikov, 1991).

Shadrikov (1994) from the standpoint of system-genetic approach to professional activity and individual abilities of the individual considers a system of objective laws that characterize individual activity, paying great attention to the psychological essence of learning as a process of forming psychological readiness for activity. The internal side of mastering the profession is the formation of readiness for professional activity on the basis of individual qualities of the subject of activity through their reorganization, reconstruction, based on the motives of the activity, purpose and conditions.

The needs of man, his interests, worldview, beliefs and attitudes, life experience, features of individual mental functions, neurodynamic qualities, personality traits are the starting point for the formation of psychological readiness for any professional activity.

As noted in the "Psychological Dictionary" (1990), the main feature of readiness for professional activity is its integrative nature, which is manifested in the ordering of internal structures, the consistency of the main components of the professional's personality, in the tenacity, stability and consistency of their functioning, i.e. professional readiness has signs, testifying to the psychological unity, the integrity of the personality of the specialist, which contribute to productive activity.

Psychological readiness for activity is generalized in the works of Dyachenko & Kandybovich (1976). They define readiness as a "purposeful expression of personality", and argue that it is formed in the process of comprehensive training and is the result of comprehensive development of personality, taking into account the requirements of the activities, profession (Dyachenko & Kandybovich, 1976). The authors consider long-term readiness "a stable personal characteristic, an essential prerequisite for successful activity", which includes the following elements of Dyachenko & Kandybovich (1976):

- a) a positive attitude to the activity, profession;
- b) adequate to the requirements of the activity, profession character traits, abilities, temperament, motivation;
- c) necessary knowledge, skills, abilities;
- d) stable, professionally important features of perception, attention, emotional and volitional processes.

On the other hand, psychological readiness can be considered as situational, short-term, as manifested on the eve of an event (competition, start, etc.).

We tend to regard the psychological readiness of the coach to solve extreme problems of sports and as a mental state, and as a complex property of the individual, which is manifested and revealed through a number of situations. Given that the management of sports activities requires a high level of development of all his mental qualities and properties, i.e. personal development, in our study we preferred a personal approach to understanding the essence of psychological readiness to make decisions in extreme situations. However, in our opinion, it is possible to form a high level of personal readiness to solve problems in extreme situations of sports activities by including the future coach in adequate training situations.

Based on the generalization of research on the problems of psychological readiness of the individual to work, we proposed a model of psychological readiness of the coach to make decisions in extreme situations of his professional activity (Fig. 1). It can be divided into several components, including motivational and executive (cognitive and operational-activity) components.

It should be noted that motivational readiness can be considered only in the context of the theory of motivation of personality, which remains a topical problem of psychology (Leontiev, 1971; Tuzov, 1982).

Fig. 1.3. *The model of psychological readiness of the coach to make decisions*

Motivation of the coach

Source: Authors' own conception

The study of motivation is to analyze the causes and factors that motivate, initiate, guide, enhance and support human activity on the way to achieving the goal. Personal motivation is associated with meeting the needs of the subject; it is a set of conditions that cause its activity and determine the direction of its activity; it is the motivating and defining choice of the subject of activity for the sake of which it is realized; a person's conscious reason underlying the choice of actions, actions of the individual, and the like.

Thus, the foreign psychologist J. Guilford (1946) reduces motivation to goal-setting attitudes of a productive nature, as in his understanding "the goal is best defined as a certain final state at which supportive activity ceases." Similar views on motivation were in S. Freud, who as a source of motivation, human activity considered the function "id" as a system of instinctive, innate urges, which seeks to maintain the psyche in a state of freedom from any excitement.

The tendency to homeostatic explanation of motivation is shown by such psychologist as Voitonis (1972), who defines "motive as a system of reactions that disturbed the balance of the organism, and is a prerequisite for the implementation of another system of reactions, organically related to the first and restoring the relative balance of the organism".

V. G. Aseev (1976) notes that the metaphysical, anti-dialectical understanding of motivation contradicts the real facts of human behavior: the state of active desire for new achievements, the search for new needs, goals, ideals, and so on. He emphasizes that only with the development, improvement of the structure of the activity itself the structure of motives develops and proposed a systematic approach to the consideration of motivation, analyzing it not just as an abstract motivational sphere, but describing its personal and individual parameters, features.

Scientifically significant in terms of motivation is the opinion of Rubinstein (1976) that a person's attitude to the environment, to others is manifested through motivation. The scientist expresses the opinion about the determinism of human activity through consciousness and the important role of volitional regulation of activity. That is why he points to the presence of conscious and unconscious impulses in the activity, Rubinstein (1976). Interpretation of Rubinstein (1976) the concept of motive is reduced to the following basic provisions: motive is understood as motivation; as a reflection in the minds of the objective driving forces of human behavior; as the experience of something personally meaningful to the individual.

Shorokhova (1982) emphasizes that the formation of personality is carried out through the development of its needs and activities in a particular social environment. However, the individual treats these external influences differently, and accordingly, depending on the level of awareness of social needs, its motivational sphere develops differently.

The theory of motivation was developed by O.M. Leontiev (1971). In particular, he emphasized that the motive not only motivates the individual to activity and determines the direction of the latter, but also gives the activity a certain personal meaning. The author presents various aspects of the problem of motivation and points out that the basis, the prerequisite

of any activity is one or another human need O.M. Leontiev (1971), and objects, means of satisfying needs must act in the mind as an inner image, as a need, as a motivation and as a goal. Thus, real objects, objects of need become motives (in the form of mental, not physical formations) as a result of their reflection in the human psyche and transformation into an internal image. Leontiev (1971) believes that historically and socially determined needs are a source of motivation for human activity.

Today there is a tendency to move from the study of individual motives to their systematic, synthetic analysis, taking into account the peculiarities of professional activity and social relationships. Thus, psychologist V.I. Kovalev (1978) speaks of the "motivational sphere" of personality. It is mostly understood as a structural and substantive characteristic of motives, its system-hierarchical reflection (Kovalev, 1978). That is why we in the study of motives that motivate the individual to make decisions in extreme situations of sports, based on a systematic approach.

We can agree with the position of V.G. Aseev (1976) that the concept of motivation can include such personality formations as interests, aspirations, attitudes, ideals, and so on. In our opinion, they need, depending on the level of awareness of the individual's need for activity, to build a clear structure of motivation.

It is established that the function of motivation to activity is realized not by the motive (Sosnovsky, 1992). At a potential stage, this is accomplished by the need for their various hierarchical relationships with motives. At the productive stage of motivation, the predominant role is played by dynamically subordinated motives in their relationships and contradictions with the personal hierarchy of meanings. In both cases, a special study of all groups of hierarchies, as well as their relationships in order to study the specific motivational and semantic structures of human orientation. Some of the components of these structures may be a kind of criteria for assessing the level of motivational readiness of the subject to a particular activity.

According to Leontiev (1971), the problem in the study of certain motives is to establish a connection between the concepts of motive and meaning of activity. Personal meaning should be considered as a specifically human, social part of life experience.

Sosnovsky (1992) points out that the motive is primary in relation to meaning only in the early stages of ontogenesis. In this case, the motive exists as a material need. In the process of personality development, meaning gradually becomes decisive in activity and participates in the choice of motives for activity. Such an analysis will be subjected to the personal

meaning of students in mastering computer technology for future professional activities.

V.A. Ivannikov (1991), concluded that the concept of motive means both the root causes of behavior and stable mental formations that motivate the choice of purpose, means and methods of action, form the meaning of action. Along with this, for reasons, we can talk about the presence of situational formations that initiate a specific activity or individual actions.

The idea of Bozhovic (1972) that the basis of a person's motivation is a stable system of interrelated motives, in which the leaders form the core of the motivational sphere and subordinate all the rest - motives are subordinate. This idea was the basis for our study of the structure of motivation, which motivates the personality of future coaches to work in extreme situations of professional activity.

In the structure of activity motives were necessarily characterized in relation to the goal to which they motivate the individual and his needs, which are reflected in the motives in the form of lack of something that causes suffering and is perceived as an objective lack of Merlin (1971).

The contribution to the principles of development of psychology of motivation and activity was made by the known Ukrainian psychologist G.S. Kostyuk (1989). He assigns a leading place in the activity of the individual to the motivational sphere, which covers a number of motives of different origin and content, the degree of generalization and awareness. He connects the motivation of human behavior with internal contradictions, conflicts between different motives, in particular, personal and socially significant G.S. Kostyuk (1989).

A number of other works are devoted to the study of the professional orientation of the individual Kovalev (1978), Shavir (1981), etc. They reveal a number of professional values of the individual: effective (possibility of self-affirmation, recognition, material motives, etc.) and meaningful (conformity to inclinations, abilities, availability of opportunities for self-improvement, etc.)

Psychologists Dyachenko & Kandybovich (1976) defends the idea of the interdependence of personality structure and motives. They emphasize, first of all, that on the basis of motives, in the course of activity such structural component of the person as orientation is formed.

Motivation of the coach can be divided into general professional and sports motivation and motivation for operational activities in certain sports situations, in extreme conditions that arise and very often manifest themselves in a competitive environment (Florea & Ungureanu, 2012).

On the basis of our generalization of scientific research in sports psychology Rodionov (2004), Volyanyuk (2006) analysis of the peculiarities of the real professional activity of coaches, a number of factors were identified that, in our opinion, may motivate the latter to perform their professional functions: the desire for self-affirmation through sports results, the success of their students; expectations of future successful results of their activities; awareness of its social significance (sense of patriotism, responsibility to society, etc.); sports excitement, a sense of struggle, love of sports and sports honor; material reward, salary; satisfaction with high sports achievements of their students in sports, etc.

The motives for the coach's behavior in specific conditions of the competition, the struggle for victory, which are saturated with numerous extreme situations, may, in our opinion, be the following:

- motives for achieving the previous goal of relatively high results;
- motives for expecting joy from victory;
- motives for professional self-affirmation and testing of their coaching abilities in extreme conditions of competitions;
- motives of sports excitement, rivalry;
- motives of aggression, hyperactivity as a means of overcoming the fear of loss, defeat;
- motives of material reward, unwillingness to receive condemnation, dissatisfaction of senior managers, etc.

In the structure of the psychological readiness of the coach to work in extreme situations, we can identify the executive component. It should be considered as a system that includes: the necessary knowledge, abilities, skills, characteristics and mental processes, i.e. all that forms the cognitive and operational components of professional readiness for management (Budnyk, 2003). It involves the assimilation by students - future coaches of integrated methodological, theoretical, methodological and practical knowledge, mastery of methods and techniques of their creative application, mastery of skills of non-standard solution of various problems in sports, competitive activities. However, as our analysis showed, the graduates of the HEI have insufficient knowledge and skills necessary for the management of athletes, especially in conditions of extreme situations of competition.

As some researchers note, it is the knowledge that is true, indisputable for a person, in which he has no doubts that constitute the basis of his beliefs, and therefore behavior. M.I. Dyachenko (1976) called this component - "orientation", understanding it as an idea of the peculiarities of professional activity, its requirements for the individual. However, the name "cognitive component", in our opinion, better reflects the psychological

characteristics of the cognitive sphere of personality and reflects the result of individual cognitive efforts and individual experience in a particular activity.

The cognitive component is a theoretical basis that must be gradually translated into practice, i.e. implemented through the executive component. To successfully perform the duties of a coach, students need to form special knowledge about the psychological characteristics of athletes and sports activities, planning and managing the preparation of athletes for competitions, knowledge of the strengths and weaknesses of the opponent and methods, ways to obtain information about future competitions, theoretical ideas about planning and decision-making algorithms in extreme situations.

However, it is quite logical that this is not enough for the coach and there is a need to talk about the operational component of readiness, namely his ability to practically solve management problems.

In understanding the essence of management skills, three directions have emerged. One of them focuses on the type of work - management. This area is characterized by definitions of this type: management skills - is the mastery of methods and techniques of management, based on the conscious use of managerial and psychological knowledge. The rest focuses on the creative nature of managerial work. Thus, the ability to perform certain activities in changing conditions on the basis of knowledge and skills is noted; possession of a complex dynamic set of mental and practical actions aimed at creative performance of professional functions; a measure of the success of heuristic management action, a measure of the effectiveness of the productive solution of a wide range of management tasks. In the third direction the definitions reflecting specificity of separate components of administrative activity are presented (Budnyk, 2004).

Despite the different approaches to the definition of management skills, it should be noted that they are based on theoretical training, taking into account the specifics of the activities where they are used, and practical actions of the professional. From the field of view of scientists falls methodological, and sometimes methodical preparation of coaches.

According to a number of scientists, coaching is as close as possible to the pedagogical activity of Rodionov (2004). Therefore, a significant interest in this regard are the works of N.V. Kuzmina, (1961) and Shchotka (2003). Based on the psychological analysis of pedagogical activity, Kuzmina (1961) identified the following components: constructive; communicative; organizational and gnostic. The author correlates the groups of knowledge and skills of the same name with these components.

Shchotka (2003) in the psychological structure of pedagogical activity distinguishes such functions as informational, mobilizing, developing, orientational, constructive, communicative, organizational, research. Moreover, the author rightly classifies the constructive, communicative, organizational and research functions as general labor functions, because they are available in all types of modern skilled labor.

We include the ability to creatively solve the tasks of coach activity:

- skills that correspond to the stages of professional management (the ability to see the problem (task) and search for the idea of its solution; the ability to implement the overall management strategy of athletes;
- ability to apply research methods (theoretical: analysis, comparison, generalization, modeling of processes in sports; practical: observation, conversation, testing, analysis of sports results, etc.);
- ability to reflect on one's own professional activity (ability to perform intellectual reflection, personal reflection, interpersonal reflection);
- the ability to manage their mental states in a competitive environment, to present the results of the achievements of their students, etc.

Thus, we can see that for creative management activities that are characteristic of a modern coach, it is necessary to have a wide range of professional skills. Forming them to the required level for a relatively limited period of study in the HEI, as practice shows, is very difficult and problematic. However, the analysis of works of domestic and foreign authors gives us the chance to draw a conclusion that the basis of an operational and activity component of professional readiness for activity is formed by the components which are called its invariants (Kandybovych, 2000).

Such invariants include, first of all, developed anticipation - the ability to predict, to determine in advance the outcome of activities. In other words, a good specialist with a high level of anticipation, i.e. the ability to accurately and far forecast, predict, even regardless of the type of activity, is able to perform their professional activities more effectively.

Specialists with a high level of self-regulation work more successfully. The latter makes it possible to resist the influence of negative functional states, to quickly adapt to the conditions of activity, to maintain the efficiency of activity and efficiency.

The high level of self-regulation can be caused both by innate features, typology of a nervous system of the trainer, and can be developed by means of special psychotechnologies. A high level of self-regulation is considered by many researchers as the most valuable professional quality.

The ability to make quick decisions is also an invariant of the effectiveness of professional activity. The ability to make decisions in extreme conditions is the most important psychological component of the activity. The decision-making process is necessarily included in any activity in one form or another. According to Lomov (1979), it is the "core of activity" and occupies a central place in the structure.

The specialist makes decisions at all stages of activity: at definition of the purpose and concrete tasks; when planning it; in the perception of current information; when choosing ways of activity; when making hypotheses; when evaluating current results. The quality of decisions depends on the effectiveness of the activity as a whole.

The above invariants are common and directly affect the effectiveness of professional activities of specialists of any category. A specific invariant that reflects the level of special in the activities of the coach is figurative thinking, managerial thinking, the ability to make meaningful decisions, etc.). Experts call creativity one of the most important professional qualities. Creative thinking is one of the important intellectual mental processes of a successful coach.

Today the focus of researchers of creativity is the problem of intellectual abilities, intellectual activity, intelligence and their relationship with the creativity of the individual, his creative thinking (Rybalka, 1996; Semenov, 1979). Not only psychologists but also teachers deal with this problem, because the intellectual activity of students, as well as their creative activity, is of great importance in the learning process and further professional activity after graduation. (Bagas, 2000; Balashov, 1996; etc.). Unfortunately, in our opinion, insufficient attention is paid to this issue during the training of coaches-teachers in the HEI.

The meaningfulness of any actions by the coach is to find the most rational and consistent actions. The managerial activity of a coach is a system of complex consecutive actions, the performance of which depends on other actions and situations of sports activity.

No less important components of the operational-activity component of the psychological readiness of coaches to make decisions in extreme situations, both in the opinion of experts and in our opinion, are communicative, perceptual, organizational and suggestive skills and abilities.

Communication of the coach, especially in the conditions of competitions, has the specific features. The reason for their originality is contained in difficult, often extreme conditions. They force to regulate styles, forms of communication. The communicative function (transfer of information) of the coach as a teacher is manifested in the optimal

communication of the specialist, in establishing the right relationships with subordinates and higher level managers, in psychological tact, which is undoubtedly his professional characteristic, and therefore we can call professional communication the leading professional quality of the coach-teacher.

It is very important in the professional activity of the coach to choose the optimal style of communication. It allows, depending on the level of communicative competence of the coach and taking into account the characteristics of his wards, the level of team development, to achieve the goal. According to scientists Volyanyuk (2006), a coach's use of one or another management style is conditioned by a number of factors:

- purpose and objectives of the activity;
- specific situation;
- coach's competence;
- the level of development of the team, athletes.

The purpose of the activity determines the management style, because in extreme situations of sports activities, the time to make a decision is often limited, often characterized by the inability to make a collective decision. There may be a situation (and it often happens) when the coach has to make an authoritarian decision and take full responsibility. In this case, the result depends on his competence, psychological readiness for it, and the ability to communicate, to influence the team.

The perceptual abilities of a coach are manifested in his ability to adequately perceive and evaluate athletes, to understand their mental states, experiences, which are naturally manifested in various sports. The ability to show empathy when necessary, to show tact in communication are important features of a modern coach.

The activity of the coach basically involves the organization of the training process, planning, monitoring the activities of the team or its individual members, a positive impact on them, creating an appropriate emotional background, etc.

There is no doubt that the coach has strong-willed qualities, the ability to instill in students confidence in victory, success, the ability in critical situations to instill in them the belief in it. Therefore, the formation of future coaches suggestive abilities is one of the tasks of the educational process.

In many works of psychologists it is noted that an important factor in regulating activities, including management, is such a personal education as self-esteem, which means that self-esteem - a component of psychological readiness for creative management (Dyachenko & Kandybovich, 1976). Self-

esteem is an assessment of oneself, one's abilities, qualities and place among other people Neimer (2003).

There are three aspects to self-esteem (as in the social attitude to any other object): cognitive - self-awareness as an object of knowledge; affective - emotional self-esteem, feelings of confidence, calm or anxiety; behavioral - a manifestation of attitude to themselves in behavioral acts (Zaluchanova, 1992).

Discussion and conclusions

As evidenced by our observations, it is characteristic that coaches who do not have a sufficient level of competence in the management of subordinates, have an inflated self-esteem.

Inflated self-esteem provokes goal setting higher than the real possibilities, neglect of the necessary information, reduction of the probability of failure, minimization of efforts to achieve the goal, "relaxing" effect of success and a strong emotional experience of failure; the need to maintain the level of self-esteem leads to a protective ignoring of failures, the explanation of their external causes, which weakens the incentive to overcome them. Sharply inflated self-esteem can create at a certain stage of activity a zone of constant failures, reduced professional motivation. The consequence of low self-esteem is passivity, fear of responsibility, tendency to set too easy tasks, underestimation of the subjective probability of success, which disrupts the impact of failures. Obviously, the inadequacy of self-esteem becomes an obstacle to professional adaptation. But also adequate high self-esteem, which is spontaneously formed in the process of professional training, can become a disorganizing factor, if it is not critically transferred from educational to professional activities. In this case, entering a professional activity, which is already characterized by a decrease in the stability of self-esteem, is complicated by its strong fluctuations. In addition, we found that there is no significant correlation between learning success and success in starting a professional activity. High self-esteem of a young specialist is often an obstacle to his acceptance into the team. The creative adaptive component, which prevails over the conformal one, is an interference at this stage.

The result of inadequate self-esteem, as a rule, is the incomplete realization of human capabilities in professional activities, in some cases - the rejection of it (Korneva, 1989). Often, during the first year of work, graduates of HEI experience a sharp drop in self-esteem, often accompanied by a steady decrease in self-confidence, a drop in motivation for professional activity, and even refusal from it. A sharp break in self-esteem has a negative

effect on the success of activities, accompanied by negative emotions, neuroticism. However, the protective preservation of inadequate self-esteem, which temporarily provides the individual with relative comfort, is even more unfavorable for the activity.

Thus, with an inadequate personal position, the subject solves the creative task as a typical (seeking to "reduce" it to cases known to him) and in this sense reproductive. "Reproductive personal position is that the subject, starting to perform the task, involves for its solution already known knowledge and tools" (Podolsky, 1987). Adequate position, on the contrary, assumes the subject's attitude to his work as a creative, which should encourage him, on the one hand, to delve into the content of the task in search of his creative moments, and on the other - to be extremely reflexive in their actions and tolerant to himself, his mistakes and failures.

Thus, the ability to adequately assess the situation and self-assessment of their capabilities in it, the decisive factors for the success of the coach in extreme situations of sports.

References

- Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, K. O. (1981). *Razvitiye lichnosti v protsesse zhiznedeyatel'nosti. Psikhologiya formirovaniya i razvitiya lichnosti* [Personal development in the process of life. Psychology of personality formation and development]. Antsyferova.
- Ananiev, B. G. (1980). *Izbrannyye psikhologicheskiye trudy* (Vol. 1)[Selected psychological works]. Pedagogy.
- Aseev, V. G. (1976) *Motivatsiya povedeniya i formirovaniye lichnosti.*[Behavior motivation and personality formation]. Mysl.
- Bagas, O. P. (2000). *Pidvyschennya psykhofizychnoyi hotovnosti kursantiv do maybutn'oyi sluzhbovoyi diyal'nosti v Prykordonnykh viys'kakh Ukrainy* [Increasing the psychophysical readiness of cadets for future service in the State Border Guard of Ukraine] (Publication No. 20.02.02) [Doctoral Dissertation, National Academy of the State Border Guard of Ukraine named after Bohdan Khmelnytsky]. Khmelnytsky.
- Balashov, V. A. (1996). *Formirovaniye professional'nykh kachestv u slushateley-pogranichnikov v protsesse professional'nogo obucheniya:* [Formation of professional qualities among students-border guards in the process of vocational training] (Publication No. 01.20.06) [Doctoral Dissertation, Pedagogical Sciences]. Khmelnytsky.
- Barabanshchikov, A. V., Glotochkin, A. D., Fedenko, N. F., & Shelyag, V. V. (1967). *Psikhologiya voynskogo kollektiva.*[Psychology of a military collective]. Voenizdat.

- Bezliudnyi, O., Kravchenko, O., Maksymchuk, B., Mishchenko, M., & Maksymchuk, I. (2019). Psycho-correction of burnout syndrome in sports educators. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 19(3), 230, 1585. <https://doi.org/10.7752/jpes.2019.03230>
- Bozhovic, L. I. (1972). *Problema razvitiya motivatsionnoy sfery rebenka. Izucheniye motivatsii povedeniya detey i podrostkov* [The problem of the development of the child's motivational sphere. Studying the motivation of the behavior of children and adolescents]. Prosveshcheniye.
- Budnyk, S. M. (2004). Tvorchy aspekty v upravlin's'kiy diyal'nosti ofitsera [Creative aspects in the management of the officer]. *Collection of scientific works*, 31(2), 55-57. Publishing House of the National Academy of the State Border Guard of Ukraine.
- Chamata, P. R. (1960). *Psikhologicheskaya gotovnost' detey k trudu i osnovnyye puti yeye formirovaniya*. [Psychological readiness of children for work and the main ways of its formation]. Soviet pedagogy.
- Derkach, A. A. Isayev, A.A., (1981). *Pedagogicheskoye masterstvo trenera* [Pedagogical skills of a coach]. Physical culture and sport.
- Dyachenko, M. I., & Kandybovich, L. A. (1976). *Psikhologicheskoye problemy gotovnosti k deyatel'nosti*. [Psychological problems of readiness for activity]. Publishing house of the Belarusian State University.
- Florea, D., & Ungureanu, C. (2012). The competition policy in the European Union. *Annals of the „Constantin Brâncuși” University of Târgu Jiu, Economy Series*, 3, 111-116. [https://www.utgjiu.ro/revista/ec/pdf/2012-03/16_DUMTRITA%20FLOAREA%20\(Ionescu\)%20111-116.pdf](https://www.utgjiu.ro/revista/ec/pdf/2012-03/16_DUMTRITA%20FLOAREA%20(Ionescu)%20111-116.pdf)
- Freud, S. (1933). *New Introductory Lectures on Psycho-Analysis*. N. Y.
- Gerasymova, I., Maksymchuk, B., Bilozerovala, M., Chernetska, Yu., Matviichuk, T., Solovyov, V., & Maksymchuk, I. (2019). Forming professional mobility in future agricultural specialists: the sociohistorical context. *Revista Romaneasca pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 11(4), 345-361. <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/195>
- Guilford, J. P. (1946). *General Psychology*. N. Y. P.
- Ivannikov, V. A. (1991). *Psikhologicheskoye mekhanizmy volevoy regulyatsii* [Psychological mechanisms of volitional regulation]. Moscow State University.
- Kandybovych, S. L. (2000). *Psikhologo-akmeologicheskoye osnovy upravlencheskoy deyatel'nosti komandira voysk radiatsionnoy, khimicheskoy i biologicheskoy zashchity* [Psychological and acmeological bases of administrative activity of the commander of the troops of radiation, chemical and biological protection] (Publication No. 19.00.13) [Doctoral Dissertation, Psychological Sciences]. Moscow.

- Karamushka, L. M. (2000). *Psykholohiya upravlinnya zakladamy seredn'oyi osvity* [Psychology of management of secondary education institutions] [Monograph]. Nika-Center.
- Korneva, L. N. (1989). Samootsenka kak mekhanizm regulyatsii professional'noy deyatel'nosti [Self-assessment as a mechanism for regulating professional activity]. *Bulletin of the Leningrad University*, 6(4), 27, 12-16.
- Kostyuk, G. S. (1989). *Navchal'no-vykhovnyy protses i psykhibnyy rozvytok osobystosti* [Educational process and mental development of personality]. In L.M. Prokolienko (Ed.), *Radyanska shkola* (pp. 608).
- Kovalev, V. I. (1978). *Psikhologicheskiye osnovy formirovaniya boyevoy aktivnosti u sovetskikh voynov* [Psychological foundations of the formation of combat activity in Soviet soldiers] [Doctoral Dissertation, Candidate of Psychological Sciences]. Moscow.
- Kuzmina, N. V. (1961). *Formirovaniye pedagogicheskikh sposobnostey* [Formation of pedagogical abilities]. Publishing house of Leningrad State University.
- Leontiev, A. N. (1971). *Potrebnosti, motivy i emotsii* [Needs, motives and emotions]. Moscow State University.
- Levitov, N. D. (1963). *Psikhologiya truda* [Labor Psychology]. Uchpedgiz, State educational pedagogical publishing house.
- Lomov, B. F. (1979). *Izucheniye cheloveka na osnove sistemnogo podkhoda. Chelovek v sisteme nauk* [The study of man on the basis of a systematic approach. Man in the system of sciences]. Nauka.
- Maksymchuk, B., Matviichuk, T., Solovyov, V., Davydenko, H., Soichuk, R., Khurtenko, O., Groshovenko, O., Stepanchenko, N., Andriychuk, Y., Grygorenko, T., Duka, T., Pidlypniak, I., Gurevych, R., Kuzmenko, V., & Maksymchuk, I. (2020). Developing Healthcare Competency in Future Teachers. *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 12(3), 24-43. <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/12.3/307>
- Melnyk, N., Bidyuk, N., Kalenskyi, A., Maksymchuk, B., Bakhmat, N., Matviienko, O. ... Maksymchuk, I. (2019). Models and organizational characteristics of preschool teachers' professional training in some EU countries and Ukraine. *Zbornik Instituta za pedagogska istrazivanja* [Proceedings of the Institute for Pedagogical Research], 51(1), 46–93. <https://doi.org/10.2298/ZIPI1901046M>
- Merlin, V. S. (1971). *Lektsii po psikhologii motivov cheloveka* [Lectures on the psychology of human motives]. Perm State Pedagogical Institute.
- Neimer, Yu.L. (Ed.), (2003). *Psikhologicheskiy slovar* [Psychological Dictionary]. Fenix.
- Nerubasska, A., & Maksymchuk, B. (2020). The Demarkation of Creativity, Talent and Genius in Humans: a Systemic Aspect. *Postmodern Openings*, 11(2), 240-255. <https://doi.org/10.18662/po/11.2/172>

- Onishchuk, I., Ikonnikova, M., Antonenko, T., Kharchenko, I., Shestakova, S., Kuzmenko, N., & Maksymchuk, B. (2020). Characteristics of Foreign Language Education in Foreign Countries and Ways of Applying Foreign Experience in Pedagogical Universities of Ukraine. *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 12(3), 44-65.
<https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/12.3/308>
- Orban-Lembryk, L. E. (2001). *Psykhoholohiia upravlinnya* [Psychology of management]. Play.
- Osnovy zahal'noyi psykhoholohiyi. (1998). [Fundamentals of General Psychology]. In S.D. Maksymenko (Ed.), *Osnovy zahal'noyi psykhoholohiyi* (pp. 256). NPU Perspektiva.
- Petrovskiy, A. V., & Yaroshevskiy, M. G. (Eds.), (1990). *Psikhologicheskii slovar* [Psychological Dictionary]. Moscow.
- Platonov, K. K. (1986). *Struktura i razvitiye lichnosti* [Structure and personality development]. Nauka.
- Podolsky, A. I. (Ed.). (1991). *Psikhologiya podgotovki spetsialistov dlya sovremennogo proizvodstva* [Psychology of training specialists for modern production]. Publishing house of Moscow State University.
- Puni, A. C. (1969). *Psikhologicheskaya podgotovka k sorevnovaniyu v sporte* [Psychological preparation for competition in sports]. Physical culture and sport.
- Rodionov, A. V. (2004). *Psikhologiya fizicheskogo vospitaniya i sporta* [Psychology of physical education and sport]. Academic Project "Mir" Foundation.
- Rubinstein, S. L. (1976). *Problemy obshchey psikhologii* [Problems of general psychology]. Pedagogy.
- Rybalka, V. V. (1996). *Psykhoholohiia rozvytku tvorchoyi osobystosti* [Psychology of creative personality development]. IZMN.
- Samarin, Yu. A. (1969). *Psikhologiya studencheskogo vozrasta i stanovleniye spetsialista* [Psychology of student age and the formation of a specialist]. *Bulletin of the higher school*, 8, 16–21.
- Semenov, I. N., & Stepanov, S. Yu. (1979). Produktivnost' lichnostnogo komponenta myshleniya pri diskursivnom reshenii zadach [The productivity of the personal component of thinking in discursive problem solving]. *Questions of psychology*, 6, 109-114.
- Shadrikov, V. D. (1994). *Deyatel'nost' i sposobnosti* [Activity and abilities]. Publishing house corporation "Logos".
- Shavir, P. L. (1981). *Psikhologiya professional'nogo samoopredeleniya v ranney yunosti* [Psychology of professional self-determination in early youth]. Pedagogy.
- Shchotka, O. P. (2003). Formuvannya psykhoholohichnoyi hotovnosti studentiv pedahohichnykh universytetiv do profesiyno-upravlins'koho samovyznachennya [Formation of psychological readiness of students of

- pedagogical universities to professional and administrative self-determination] (Publication: 19.00.07) [Doctoral Dissertation, Institute of Psychology named after G.S. Kostyuk of the Academy of Pedagogical Sciences]. Ukraine.
- Sheremet, M., Leniv, Z., Loboda, V., & Maksymchuk, B. (2019). The development level of smart information criterion for specialists' readiness for inclusion implementation in education. *Information Technologies and Learning Tools*, 72, 273-285. <https://doi.org/10.33407/itlt.v72i4.2561>
- Shorokhova, E. V. (1982). *Tendentsii issledovaniya lichnosti v sovetskoy psikhologii. Problemy psikhologii lichnosti* [Trends in personality research in Soviet psychology. Problems of personality psychology]. Nauka.
- Skorikov, V. B. (1991). *Psikhologicheskaya gotovnost' rabotnika k rukovodstvu nauchno-proizvodstvennym kollektivom* [Psychological readiness of an employee to manage a research and production team] (Publication No. 19.00.05) [Doctoral Dissertation, Psychological Sciences]. State Academy of Management named after V.S. Ordzhonikidze.
- Sosnovsky, B. A. (1992). *Motivatsionno-smysloryye obrazovaniya v psikhologicheskoy strukture lichnosti* [Motivational and semantic formations in the psychological structure of the personality]. (Publication No. 19.00.01) [Doctoral Dissertation, Psychological Sciences]. Moscow State University.
- Timchenko, A.V. (1995). *Problema psikhologicheskoy gotovnosti voyennogo spetsialista k ekstremnomu deystviyu v sostoyanii emotsional'nogo stressa* [The problem of psychological readiness of a military specialist for emergency action in a state of emotional stress]. (Publication No. 19.00.01) [Doctoral Dissertation, Candidate of Psychological Sciences]. Kharkov University of Internal Affairs of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine.
- Tuzov, A. P. (1982). *Motivatsiya protivopravnogo povedeniya nesovershennoletnikh* [Motivation of unlawful behavior of minors]. Vishcha.
- Voitonis, N. Yu. (1972). *Problema motivov povedeniya i yeye izucheniye* [The problem of motives of behavior and its study]. *Psychology*, 2(2), 47–52.
- Volyanyuk, N. Yu. (2006). *Psykholohiya profesijnobo stanovlennya trenera* [Psychology of professional development of a coach]. Volyn regional printing house.
- Zaluchenova, E. A. (1992). *Samoosenka v deyatelnosti studentov* [Self-assessment in the activities of students]. Mysl.